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ABSTRACTS

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Formulation and Evaluation of Mosapride Citrate Dihydrate Nanoemulsion

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Abstract: Formulating and Evaluating a Nanoemulsion with Mosapride Citrate Dihydrate for Effective Treatment of Dyspepsia and GERD. Treating digestive issues such as dyspepsia and GERD often involves the use of gastroprokinetic agents like Mosapride Citrate. However, the limited aqueous solubility of this drug can hinder its bioavailability. In response, this study focuses on creating nanoemulsions loaded with Mosapride to boost its solubility and increase its dissolution rate. Innovative nanoemulsion formulations were successfully prepared through the high-energy emulsification method, utilizing top-quality ingredients such as linseed oil, Tween 80, and Polyoxymer 127. Comprehensive characterization of the formulations included measurements of globule size, zeta potential, polydispersity index, drug content, in vitro drug release, stability under different conditions, as well as imaging techniques such as transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). The results of solubility studies proved the superior solubility of mosapride when incorporated in the nanoemulsions, surpassing that of the pure drug. The optimized nanoemulsion exhibited a remarkable globule size of 13.5nm, impressive 92.33% drug release within 60 minutes and remained stable for a period of 3 months. The confirmation of nano-range globule size was obtained through TEM images, solidifying the efficacy of the developed nanoemulsion. In summary, the newly created nanoemulsion containing mosapride has great potential as a delivery method for enhancing the solubility and dissolution rate of the drug, which is known to have poor water-solubility. Such improvements could result in increased bioavailability and effectiveness in treating patients.

Keywords: Mosapride citrate, nanoemulsion, solubility enhancement, dyspepsia.

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